

**RECYCLING
POST-CONSUMER
FIBREBOARD
WASTE INTO NEW
PARTICLEBOARD**

**PROJECT INNOVATION
FACTSHEET**

Contributing to the EU's circular bioeconomy, reintegrating end-of-life panels into production helps optimise wood use, extend product lifecycles, stores carbon and reduce dependence on virgin wood.

APPLICATIONS

Particleboard (PB) is a cost-effective, versatile wood-based panel made by pressing glued woodchips and fines into a three-layer board under heat. It is suitable for surfacing and widely used in furniture, shelving, upholstery, and flooring underlayers.

ACHIEVEMENTS

- Fines from post-consumer fibreboard produced with a chemical-free and water-free mechanical process were successfully used in the particleboard surface layer to substitute the standard wood mix.
- Lab results were promising up to substitution rates of 30%.
- An industrial trial at 20% on a conventional line confirmed process stability and product performance.
- Physical and mechanical properties comparable to reference panels, EN 312 met, and formaldehyde emissions below E05.
- Stable process production with no gluing changes and uniform appearance when particle size was well controlled.

FUTURE CHALLENGES

Further work should focus on improving fines handling and preparation to achieve a more homogeneous surface layer, as occasional defects at higher substitution levels were linked to fines agglomeration during storage and conveying.

PARTNERS

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